

**Management of Major Exsanguination in Austere
Environments: Recommended Therapeutic Armamentarium
for the Wilderness and Expedition Medic**

By: Dr Abu Sayeed Galib

Diploma in Remote and Offshore Medicine

Module C10: Wilderness and Expedition Medicine

The Royal College of Surgeons of Edinburgh

(Modified: 09.03.2025)

Title Change Note: Changed from [Management of Major Exsanguination in Austere Environments] to [Management of Major Exsanguination in Austere Environments: Recommended Therapeutic Options for the Wilderness and Expedition Medic] to better reflect the content of the report.

Major Exsanguination

Abstract

Trauma forms a major part of the incidents seen by the Wilderness and Expedition medic (Ikeda et al., 2019). It is thus desirable, that he or she remains well versed in the management protocols, required to care for the injured patient (Cooke et al., 2000). One of the most life-threatening events is major exsanguination, which could lead to the quick demise of the patient (Chang et al., 2017). Hence it is pertinent to be knowledgeable of both the current and future treatment options (Jamal et al., 2021a). These can significantly contribute in reducing the overall morbidity and mortality of the personnel under care. Various options like tourniquets, compression bandages, medications and other adjuncts have been developed over many years and can form a part of the arsenal of any WEM medic. This paper provides information on current and future modalities of care specifically for major exsanguination.

Major Exsanguination

Major Exsanguination in Austere Environments

A major haemorrhage at a remote area needs to be immediately attended to prevent both morbidity and mortality. The medical team should have in its disposal a wide array of resources to control the bleeding and prevent death. For several years now intensive research in various modalities and options for exsanguination intervention is being carried out. Significant advances have been made with the emergence of such items as haemostatic agents, compression bandages, clamps, specialised tourniquets, etc. The objective, of this paper, is to review, existing literature, to understand the current accepted treatment agents and modalities. Promising new approaches and items which may find adoption in austere environments is also dealt with.

The problem

Major exsanguination has been a significant contributor of mortality in the prehospital setting. Timely intervention using the right tools and modalities remains of vital importance. The WEM medic is expected to provide optimal levels of care in case of major injuries. Significant advances have been made in exsanguination management, but it is important to understand the applicability, efficacy, safety and limitations of the various agents, tools, and items currently available.

Background

War casualty and prehospital statistics, and some major expedition casualties all point to the fact, that major exsanguination remains a challenge to the uninitiated and to the

Major Exsanguination

experienced medic alike. Modern medical research has been able to come up with significant advances to address this critical problem. It is up to the medic to remain abreast of the current options, so that a timely and decisive intervention can be made.

Initial treatment

Direct pressure on the bleeding site remains the method of choice, as the medic/s prepare for more definitive measures. Collateral circulation and bleeding resumes in 30-60 secs. A pressure dressing may then be applied, as a temporizing measure.

Extremity Tourniquets (TQ)

Tourniquets (Drew et al., 2015), had been the mainstay of bleeding control from the first times of modern medicine. Evidence suggests their use over more than 2 millennia. Reports found them to be highly effective in preventing exsanguination in combat scenarios. Applied correctly and in a timely fashion, they have proved, that major exsanguination can be prevented at the earliest. Once applied, they should be periodically assessed to prevent complications, like limb ischaemia, rigor, pain, or palsies.

Several commercial variants have been developed, and about 4 of them, meet the CoTCCC criteria, for use in austere and combat environments. These are **Combat Action TQ(C-A-T)**, **Special Operation Forces Tactical TQ(SOF-TT)**, two variants, and the **Emergency and Military TQ(EMT)**. As of now no approved tourniquet has been found to be superior to any other.

TQs should be used as early as possible, in any major arterial bleeding, applied proximal and close to the wound. A second tourniquet may be required. Common mistakes to avoid are, delaying TQ use, not tightening enough, loosening TQ before 2 hours, not following

Major Exsanguination

appropriate technique, not protecting TQs from the elements, while in storage. As such all WEM medics, should peruse the literature and practice proper TQ use.

Junctional Tourniquets

These new age TQs are used when extremity TQs or pressure dressing is ineffective, in preventing exsanguination. FDA has currently approved **SAM junctional TQ(SJT)**, **Combat Ready Clamp (CRoC)**, and **Junctional Emergency Treatment Tool (JETT)**. An additional product, the **Abdominal Aortic Junctional TQ(AAJT)** has partial approval from FDA.

Significant reading, preparation, and practice on part of the advanced WEM medic is required to make these tools effective, under emergency situations. The consideration of space and bulk during carriage needs to be given careful consideration, to prevent any hindrance to the expedition objectives. Nevertheless, junctional devices, should be kept under consideration, when planning medical stock, to be carried on major expeditions,

Systemic Haemostatic agents

Tranexamic acid (Roberts et al., 2013) has gained wide popularity in the prehospital setting, due its feasibility of application, and improved patient outcomes in several reports. Since the only criteria is major bleeding, it can be used for all cases of evident and suspected haemorrhage. The BATT score can be an additional aide to the decision making. The only limitation is that it should be administered within three hours of the incident, to prevent increased risk of side effects.

Freeze dried lyophilized plasma (FDP)(Mok et al., 2021), provides logistical advantages over Fresh Frozen Plasma(FFP), and is being routinely used in prehospital and austere settings.

Reviews have identified a similar outcome profile as FFP, and a reduced need of blood

Major Exsanguination

transfusion after transfer to an in-hospital setting. The improved biochemical and coagulation profile of post treatment blood samples and lack of serious side effects, makes this an agent of choice for austere environments.

Fibrinogen Concentrate (FC), is slowly being adopted by the combat forces around the world. Initial reports suggest it can be used routinely in austere environments and can prove beneficial in controlling haemorrhage(Ziegler et al., 2021). Clinical studies have indicated FC induces rapid clot formation, increased clot strength, and decreased blood transfusion requirements (Winearls et al., 2017). Several clinical trials have established the feasibility and safety of FC in the prehospital setting.

Local Haemostatic Agents

Contact agents, such as Kaolin and Chitosan has shown promise as first line agents in the management of exsanguination. Extended trials and field reports under combat circumstances, have now placed **QuikClot Combat Gauze** (kaolin based) as the primary choice for major bleeding (Basadonna, 2012). Various clinical trials and field reports suggest that Combat Gauze is effective in preventing major haemorrhage in the prehospital setting (Leonard et al., 2016), and is effective even in the face of haemodilution(Kim et al., 2020).

New guidelines have incorporated chitosan impregnated **Celox Gauze** (Pozza & Millner, 2011), and **ChitoGauze**, as secondary choices under combat situations. Reports from military and in-hospital settings have indicated that the later agents are at least equally effective, with no major safety concerns, and have been in use for more than a decade (Bennett et al., 2014). Chitosan based products should be used with caution on

Major Exsanguination

persons with known shellfish allergy (*Overview of Agents Used for Emergency Hemostasis - PMC*, n.d.).

Advances and experimental options

Resuscitative endovascular balloon occlusion of aorta (REBOA) (Jamal et al., 2021b), is being used to control torso haemorrhage, and may find wider adoption, in the future. Being relatively easy to apply in the field, and reports of successful case studies, may make it a definitive option in the future.

ResQFoam is a compound that is used in torso haemorrhage. It acts as an expanding tamponade. The preparation and application need training, and could lead to serious consequences, if used by untrained personnel. Nevertheless, initial field reports are encouraging.

XSTAT, is a promising bioengineered compound that possesses several characteristics, that makes it ideal for used in penetrating trauma of the extremities. Efficacy, safety, and feasibility reports, makes it one of the most promising new agents.

Conclusion

Modern technology and the products thereof, will play a vital role, in ensuring survival under austere environments. Some of the items, mentioned above, has already proved to be safe and efficacious. The feasibility of application will vary from environment to environment. The author sincerely hopes, that the Wilderness and Expedition fraternity, takes full advantage of the current, emerging, and future methodologies, to ensure they deliver the best medical care possible.

Bibliography

- Basadonna, G. (2012). QuikClot Combat Gauze for Hemorrhage Control. *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine, 27*(2), 217–217. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1049023X12000490>
- Bennett, B. L., Littlejohn, L. F., Kheirabadi, B. S., Butler, F. K., Kotwal, R. S., Dubick, M. A., & Bailey, J. A. (2014). Management of External Hemorrhage in Tactical Combat Casualty Care: Chitosan-Based Hemostatic Gauze Dressings--TCCC Guidelines-Change 13-05. *Journal of Special Operations Medicine: A Peer Reviewed Journal for SOF Medical Professionals, 14*(3), 40–57.
- Chang, R., Eastridge, B. J., & Holcomb, J. B. (2017). Remote Damage Control Resuscitation in Austere Environments. *Wilderness & Environmental Medicine, 28*(2S), S124–S134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wem.2017.02.002>
- Cooke, F. J., Sabin, C., & Zuckerman, J. N. (2000). A Study of the Incidence of Accidents Occurring during an Arctic Expedition: Another Important Aspect of Travel Medicine? *Journal of Travel Medicine, 7*(4), 205–207. <https://doi.org/10.2310/7060.2000.00061>
- Drew, B., Bennett, B. L., & Littlejohn, L. (2015). Application of Current Hemorrhage Control Techniques for Backcountry Care: Part One, Tourniquets and Hemorrhage Control Adjuncts. *Wilderness & Environmental Medicine, 26*(2), 236–245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wem.2014.08.016>
- Ikeda, A., Ohno, G., Otani, S., Watanabe, K., & Imura, S. (2019). Disease and injury statistics of Japanese Antarctic research expeditions during the wintering period: Evaluation of 6837 cases in the 1st-56th parties - Antarctic health report in 1956-2016. *International Journal of Circumpolar Health, 78*(1), 1611327. <https://doi.org/10.1080/22423982.2019.1611327>

Major Exsanguination

Jamal, L., Saini, A., Quencer, K., Altun, I., Albadawi, H., Khurana, A., Naidu, S., Patel, I.,

Alzubaidi, S., & Oklu, R. (2021a). Emerging approaches to pre-hospital hemorrhage control: A narrative review. *Annals of Translational Medicine*, *9*(14), 1192.

<https://doi.org/10.21037/atm-20-5452>

Jamal, L., Saini, A., Quencer, K., Altun, I., Albadawi, H., Khurana, A., Naidu, S., Patel, I.,

Alzubaidi, S., & Oklu, R. (2021b). Emerging approaches to pre-hospital hemorrhage control: A narrative review. *Annals of Translational Medicine*, *9*(14), 1192.

<https://doi.org/10.21037/atm-20-5452>

Kim, K., Shim, H., Jung, P. Y., Kim, S., Choi, Y. U., Bae, K. S., Lee, J. K., & Jang, J. Y. (2020).

Effectiveness of kaolin-impregnated hemostatic gauze use in preperitoneal pelvic packing for patients with pelvic fractures and hemodynamic instability: A propensity score matching analysis. *PLOS ONE*, *15*(7), e0236645.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0236645>

Leonard, J., Zietlow, J., Morris, D., Berns, K., Eyer, S., Martinson, K., Jenkins, D., & Zietlow, S.

(2016). A multi-institutional study of hemostatic gauze and tourniquets in rural civilian trauma. *Journal of Trauma and Acute Care Surgery*, *81*(3), 441–444.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/TA.0000000000001115>

Mok, G., Hoang, R., Khan, M. W., Pannell, D., Peng, H., Tien, H., Nathens, A., Callum, J.,

Karkouti, K., Beckett, A., & da Luz, L. T. (2021). Freeze-dried plasma for major trauma – Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Trauma and Acute Care Surgery*,

90(3), 589–602. <https://doi.org/10.1097/TA.0000000000003012>

Overview of Agents Used for Emergency Hemostasis—PMC. (n.d.). Retrieved 28 April 2022,

from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4869418/>

Major Exsanguination

- Pozza, M., & Millner, R. W. J. (2011). Celox (chitosan) for haemostasis in massive traumatic bleeding: Experience in Afghanistan. *European Journal of Emergency Medicine, 18*(1), 31–33. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MEJ.0b013e32833a5ee4>
- Roberts, I., Shakur, H., Coats, T., Hunt, B., Balogun, E., Barnetson, L., Cook, L., Kawahara, T., Perel, P., Prieto-Merino, D., Ramos, M., Cairns, J., Guerriero, C., Roberts, I., Shakur, H., Coats, T., Hunt, B., Balogun, E., Barnetson, L., ... Guerriero, C. (2013). *The CRASH-2 trial: A randomised controlled trial and economic evaluation of the effects of tranexamic acid on death, vascular occlusive events and transfusion requirement in bleeding trauma patients*. NIHR Journals Library.
- Winearls, J., Wulschleger, M., Wake, E., Hurn, C., Furyk, J., Ryan, G., Trout, M., Walsham, J., Holley, A., Cohen, J., Shuttleworth, M., Dyer, W., Keijzers, G., Fraser, J. F., Presneill, J., & Campbell, D. (2017). Fibrinogen Early In Severe Trauma study (FEISTY): Study protocol for a randomised controlled trial. *Trials, 18*, 241. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-017-1980-x>
- Ziegler, B., Bachler, M., Haberfellner, H., Niederwanger, C., Innerhofer, P., Hell, T., Kaufmann, M., Maegele, M., Martinowitz, U., Nebl, C., Oswald, E., Schöch, H., Schenk, B., Thaler, M., Treichel, B., Voelckel, W., Zykova, I., Wimmer, C., & Fries, D. (2021). Efficacy of prehospital administration of fibrinogen concentrate in trauma patients bleeding or presumed to bleed (FlinTIC). *European Journal of Anaesthesiology, 38*(4), 348–357. <https://doi.org/10.1097/EJA.0000000000001366>